

D8.4

Interim report covering Months 1-24

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D8.4/ Interim report covering Months 1-24

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Abstract

MYRIAD-EU is a Horizon 2020-funded project running for four years, from September 2021 to August 2025. It brings together a leading interdisciplinary, intersectoral consortium of research organisations (CMCC, UKRI BGS, Deltares, IIASA, CICERO, MPI, TNO), universities (VUA, ULL, ASE, UHAM), Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) (Risklayer, Arctik), large companies (Aon), government agencies (CICYTEX), NGOs (WIEA), and umbrella associations (FEHRL, HOTREC).

MYRIAD-EU's vision is to catalyse the required paradigm shift in how complex natural hazard risks are assessed and managed. To achieve this, the overall aim of MYRIAD-EU is that by the end of the project we will be able to develop forward-looking disaster risk management pathways that assess trade-offs and synergies of various strategies across sectors, hazards, and scales. We co-develop a framework, tools, and methods to help stakeholders achieve the aim. This is done through five multi-scale Pilots (North Sea, Canary Islands, Scandinavia, Danube, Veneto). Each Pilot focuses on forward-looking DRM solutions to real-world sustainability challenges faced by six key sectors: infrastructure & transport, food & agriculture, ecosystems & forestry, energy, finance, and tourism.

This report highlights some of the key outputs produced during the first two years of the project. The aim is to provide interested parties with highlights of some of the major accomplishments so far. The report is explicitly not intended to provide a comprehensive overview of all the work conducted until month 24. For an extensive overview of our results, the reader is encouraged to visit the Library section of our project website (www.myriadproject.eu) and our Zenodo MYRIAD-EU community page (<https://zenodo.org/communities/myriad-eu>). Instead, the main scientific outcomes are presented using a series of standalone 'research briefs'. Each research brief is based on an individual deliverable or research paper that has been published, and contains an overview of key highlights, recommendations, context, and contact details of the leading author. They are intended as a high-level entry point for key results, with clear links to their background reports and papers. Communication highlights and a brief outlook for the second two year of the project are also presented.

Dissemination level of the document

- Public
- Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the European Commission Services)
- Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the European Commission Services)

Version History

Version	Date	Authors/Reviewers	Description
V1	02/11/2023	Philip Ward (VUA), Marleen de Ruyter (VUA), Kelley De Polt (MPI)	Draft version submitted to Quality Unit for review
V2	24/11/2023	Philip Ward (VUA), Marleen de Ruyter (VUA), Kelley De Polt (MPI)	Revised following internal review. Contains formatted research briefs

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1 Introduction

1.1 MYRIAD-EU aims and objectives

Natural hazards in the EU have exacted a heavy toll, resulting in approximately ~236,000 fatalities and over €640 billion in economic losses since 2000. The last decade saw huge scientific advances in understanding natural hazard risks, and within the EU there has been a shift in practice from managing hazards to managing risks. Nevertheless, most research and policy still addresses risk from a single-hazard, single-sector, perspective. This presents obstacles for addressing real-world challenges. Firstly, multiple hazards can have interrelated effects on risk. For example, an earthquake could trigger a landslide; dry conditions could amplify the likelihood of forest fires; a combination of rainfall and storm surge could cause compound flooding; or a region could face consecutive hazards. **How can risk be better managed by considering these interrelated effects?** Secondly, disaster risk management (DRM) measures taken to reduce risk from one hazard may increase risk from another hazard. For example, wood-frame buildings may perform well in earthquakes, but could sustain high damages during flooding. **How can we better account for these dynamic feedbacks between risk drivers?** Thirdly, these interrelated effects have impacts across sectors. For example, there are trade-offs and synergies between maintaining the sustainable use of our land and marine regions while meeting increasing demand for sustainable energy and food and reducing risks. **How can we account for these trade-offs and synergies across sectors, regions, and hazards?**

The aforementioned challenges exist within the context of an increasingly interconnected world, increased pressure for space, and climate change, in which the magnitude and frequency of single and multi-hazards are changing at an unprecedented rate. **A paradigm shift is needed to successfully address these kinds of complex questions and challenges**, in which science and practice move from a single-hazard, single-sector, risk perspective towards a multi-risk, multi-sector, systemic approach. The need for such an approach is also a guiding principle of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction. Whilst disaster risk reduction (DRR) is central to EU strategies and policies including the European Green Deal, Adaptation Strategy, and Civil Protection Mechanism, as well as the Paris Agreement (PA) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), common frameworks for assessing and managing multi-hazard risk do not exist yet.

MYRIAD-EU's vision is to catalyse the required paradigm shift in how complex natural hazard risks are assessed and managed. To achieve this, **the overall aim of MYRIAD-EU is that by the end of the project we will be able to develop forward-looking disaster risk management pathways** that assess trade-offs and synergies of various strategies across sectors, hazards, and scales. We co-develop a framework, tools, and methods to help stakeholders achieve the aim. This is done via five multi-scale Pilots (North Sea, Canary Islands, Scandinavia, Danube, Veneto). Each Pilot focuses on forward-looking DRM solutions to real-world sustainability challenges faced by six key sectors: infrastructure & transport, food & agriculture, ecosystems & forestry, energy, finance, and tourism. The overall vision, aim, and key expected outcomes are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overall aim and vision of MYRIAD-EU, and a selection of main expected outcomes

1.2 Purpose of this report

This report highlights some of the key outputs produced during the first two years of the project. The aim is to provide interested parties with highlights of some of the major accomplishments so far. The report is explicitly not intended to provide a comprehensive overview of all the work conducted until month 24. For an extensive overview of our results, the reader is encouraged to visit the *Library* section of our project website (www.myriadproject.eu) and our Zenodo MYRIAD-EU community page (<https://zenodo.org/communities/myriad-eu>). Instead, the main scientific outcomes are presented using a series of standalone ‘research briefs’ in section 2. Each research brief is based on an individual deliverable or research paper that has been published, and it contains an overview of key highlights, recommendations, context, and contact details of the leading author. They are intended as a high-level entry point for key results, with clear links to their background reports and papers. Communication highlights are presented in section 3. Finally, in Section 4 we provide a brief outlook for the second two years of the project.

1.3 MYRIAD-EU in a nutshell

MYRIAD-EU is a Horizon 2020-funded project running for four years, from September 2021 to August 2025. It brings together a leading interdisciplinary, intersectoral consortium of research organisations (*Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC)*, *British Geological Survey (UKRI BGS)*, *Deltares (DRES)*, *International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)*, *Center for International Climate Research (CICERO)*, *Max Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry*

(MPI), Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (TNO)), universities (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VUA), Universidad de la Laguna (ULL), Bucharest University of Economic Studies (ASE), Universität Hamburg (UHAM)), Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) (Risklayer, Arctic), large companies (Aon), government agencies (Centro de Investigaciones Científicas y Tecnológicas de Extremadura (CICYTEX)), NGOs (Wetlands International European Association (WIEA)), and umbrella associations (Forum of European National Highway Research Laboratories (FEHRL), Confederation of National Associations of Hotels, Restaurants, Cafés and Similar Establishments in the European Union and European Economic Area (HOTREC)). The consortium brings together knowledge and experience on: the key concepts of MYRIAD-EU (systemic risk, risk dynamics, risk scenarios, decision-making, DRR/adaptation, Nature-Based Solutions); different hazards (meteorological, climatological, geological, biological); different methods, models, and tools (e.g. hazard models, impact models, loss databases, decision-support tools, participatory methods, machine learning); science communication; and the six sectors of MYRIAD-EU of key importance for the EU (i.e. infrastructure & transport, food & agriculture, ecosystems & forestry, energy, finance, tourism).

MYRIAD-EU is working on pilot studies in five different pilot regions (Figure 2). These regions serve as our laboratories with a combination of unique geological and meteorological characteristics. Some study a rather small geographic area, like Veneto in Italy; others stretch across several countries, like the Danube region. Each pilot houses a range of different hazards, sectors and interrelations between them. The diversity of the pilots makes it possible to adapt the outcomes of MYRIAD-EU to other areas in Europe.

Figure 2: Overview of MYRIAD-EU sectors, hazards, pilots and key challenge addressed within each pilot

The project workflow and timeline are designed around 5 major steps, as shown in Figure 3. Months 1-9 were dedicated to Step 1, “Common Baseline”. During the first 6 months of this step the vast majority of the scientific work was dedicated to Work Package (WP) 1 “Diagnosis”, in which all consortium partners were involved. This proved to be a useful strategy for starting a project with the complexity of MYRIAD-EU. It allowed time and resources for partners to get to understand each other’s perspectives, challenges, and ways of working, as well as for us to properly review past methods, models, tools, policies, policy-making processes, and governance for multi-hazard, multi-

risk management. This was essential for the “handshake” with WP2 (Framework and synthesis), during Months 6-9, in which the baseline knowledge from WP1 was used to co-develop an initial framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, systemic risk management. At Month 10, we moved into Step 2 “Initial Design & development”, which ran until Month 24. During this step, all scientific WPs have been in full swing. This report provides several non-exhaustive highlights up to this halfway point of the project.

Figure 3: Timeline of MYRIAD-EU, with the interim reporting period (M1-24) shown in the red box

1.4 Highlights from the first 2 years of MYRIAD-EU

Through this process, MYRIAD-EU achieved all its expected results of the two years. Several major achievements are listed below, and in Section 2 we zoom in on a selection of these in short standalone ‘Research Briefs’.

- Completing a thorough diagnosis of multi-hazard, multi-risk management challenges, including the publication of a handbook of multi-hazard, multi-risk concepts, definitions, and indicators and a report on policies, policy-making processes, and governance for multi-hazard, multi-risk management (WP1);
- Launching a WIKI-platform (www.disasterriskgateway.net) (WP1) and designing a prototype dashboard, for further development during 2023 (WP2);
- Co-developing an initial framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, systemic risk management (WP2), and testing its usefulness with our Pilot Core Users and Pilot Stakeholders during five Pilot Workshops (one in each pilot region (WP3));
- Co-designing the research work in the Pilot Studies in collaboration with stakeholders and project partners (WP3);
- Designing methods for capturing evidence of dynamic feedbacks between risk drivers, by designing studies using various novel methods including: interviews, literature reviews, AI-based approaches, and using remote sensing data to map recovery times (WP4);
- Developing a first global multi-hazard database, MYRIAD-HESA (WP5);
- Developing a conceptual approach for designing Dynamic Adaptive Pathways in a Multi-Risk setting (DAPP-MR) (WP6);
- Working on developing forward-looking DRM pathways by: (1) implementing feedback from pilot leads on their experience with the proposed collaborative systems analysis approach

and; (2) facilitating the assessment of multiple possible pathways to adapt to current and future multi-risk challenges using DAPP-MR (WP6);

- Developing MYRIAD-EU as a well-recognised brand through a bold graphic charter, and a range of communication and dissemination activities, including: website with news and blogs, active X and LinkedIn accounts, and organisation of /participation in scientific, practice, and policy events, including: UNDRR European Forum for Disaster Risk Reduction, DRMKC annual seminar, RISK KAN seminars, and annual meetings of practitioner organisations such as ERIAFF, FEHRL, HOTREC;
- Holding three General Assemblies, as well as regular communication with External Advisory Board, Sectoral Sounding Board, and Early Career Researcher Board;
- Published >10 peer-reviewed scientific papers relating to MYRIAD-EU, all of which can be found on our [MYRIAD-EU Zenodo Community page](#).

1.5 MYRIAD-EU Early Career Researchers Board

MYRIAD-EU prides itself on the high and integral involvement of Early Career Researchers (ECRs) within the project, both in terms of content and management. MYRIAD-EU has an Early Career Researchers Board (ECRB), consisting of 4 to 5 elected members (with gender balance). During the first 24 months of the project, the ECRB consisted of: Judith Claassen (chair year 1), Kelley De Polt (chair year 2), Robert Šakić Trogrlić, and Timothy Tiggeloven. During the second half of the project, the ECRB consists of: Julius Schlumberger (chair year 3), Sophie Buijs (chair year 4), Sara García González, María García Vaquero, and Davide Mauro Ferrario. The role of chair is held for one year.

During the initial board's term, the ECRB achieved several notable accomplishments. These included the organisation of ECR-focused sessions at the MYRIAD-EU General Assemblies (Gas) in 2022 and 2023. These sessions were structured as a research pitch session in 2022 and a poster session in 2023, both with active discussions following. Additionally, during the GAs, the ECRB played an essential role in conducting ice-breaker activities in 2021, 2022, and 2023. Furthermore, the ECRB initiated other activities, such as designing and distributing surveys to gauge the level of engagement and involvement of Early Career Researchers (ECRs) in the project. The feedback gathered from these surveys was then relayed directly to the management team by the ECRB chair (who is also a member of the management team), with the aim of identifying areas for improvement or commending areas which served the ECR well.

Looking ahead to the second board's term, the ECRB plans to continue these endeavors. Additionally, the board will launch initiatives focused on increasing skills development and fostering discussions about potential future career paths. This initiative will leverage the diverse expertise available within the consortium.

The Management Team of MYRIAD-EU sees the establishment of such an ECRB as a key contributor to the success of the project, and would recommend it to future projects as a good practice.

2 MYRIAD-EU research briefs

November 2023

Research brief: MYRIAD-EU research agenda: towards disaster risk management pathways in multi-(hazard-)risk assessment

MYRIAD-EU project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003276

MYRIAD-EU research agenda: towards disaster risk management pathways in multi-(hazard-)risk assessment

Highlights

- We have developed a methodology to determine impact-relevant durations for the analysis of climate extremes based upon local context of impacts.
- We identify five challenges that hinder progress towards a more multi-(hazard) risk approach in practice:
 - There exists diverse language on multi-(hazard-)risk and a lack of overview of existing methods and tools;
 - There is a lack of a clear framework and guidelines for multi-(hazard-)risk assessment and management;
 - We have a poor understanding of dynamic feedbacks between hazard, exposure, and vulnerability;
 - Only a few studies assess the effectiveness of Disaster Risk Management (DRM) measures across hazards, sectors, and time horizons;
 - Distinct lack of in-depth case-studies on multi-(hazard-)risk assessment and management.
- To address these challenges, the MYRIAD-EU project argues for an approach that addresses multi-(hazard-)risk management through the lens of sustainability challenges that cut across sectors, regions, and hazards.

Recommendations

- We present a research agenda to help us move towards the aforementioned approach. This agenda is being implemented within the MYRIAD-EU project, and includes the following key components:
 - Establishing a set of common multi-(hazard-)risk definitions and concepts and an overview of existing methods and tools.
 - Co-developing a framework for multi-(hazard-)risk assessment and management.
 - Increasing understanding of dynamic feedbacks between hazard, exposure, and vulnerability
 - Developing future scenarios of plausible multi-(hazard-)risk.
 - Assessing the effectiveness of DRM measures across hazards, sectors, and time horizons
 - Testing of approaches in in-depth case studies on multi-(hazard-)risk assessment and management.

Context

Recent decades have seen a move from managing hazards to managing risks. However, the majority of natural-hazard risk research still focuses on single hazards. Internationally, there are increasing calls for more attention on multi-hazard and multi-risks. Within the

European Union (EU), the concepts of multi-(hazard-)risk assessment and management have taken centre stage in recent years.

This perspective paper was written and published at the start of the Horizon-2020 funded MYRIAD-EU project (Multi-hazard and sYstemic framework for enhancing Risk-Informed mAnagement and Decision-making in the E.U.). It presents several challenges for multi-(hazard-)risk management as outlined in several research projects. It then sets out the MYRIAD-EU team's research agenda for addressing these challenges. We argue for an approach that addresses multi-(hazard-)risk management through the lens of sustainability challenges that cut across sectors, regions, and hazards. In this approach, the starting point is a specific sustainability challenge, rather than an individual hazard or sector, and trade-offs and synergies are examined across sectors, regions, and hazards. We argue for in-depth case studies in which various approaches for multi-(hazard-)risk management are co-developed and tested in practice. This agenda is guiding the work that is being carried out within the MYRIAD-EU project.

Picture of the MYRIAD-EU team at the 3rd General Assembly in Venice

Want to know more?

- **Full reference:** Ward, P.J., 2022. Invited perspectives: A research agenda towards disaster risk management pathways in multi-(hazard-)risk assessment. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22, 1487-1497, doi:10.5194/nhess-22-1487-2022
- **Link to paper:** <https://nhess.copernicus.org/articles/22/1487/2022/>
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November 2023

Research brief: Establishing a common baseline for multi-hazard, multi-risk research in a European context: Key observations and recommendations

MYRIAD-EU project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003276

Establishing a common baseline for multi-hazard, multi-risk research in a European context: Key observations and recommendations

Highlights

- We developed a **Handbook**, which builds on an extensive body of work, particularly internationally recognised glossaries, to strengthen consensus across the hazard and risk community through a common understanding of multi-hazard, multi-risk terminology and concepts.
- We proposed draft **multi-hazard, multi-risk indicators** and a roadmap for testing their further development and application in disaster risk management.
- We reviewed methods, models and tools for multi-hazard, multi-risk assessment and management in order to serve as an information resource and starting point in the MYRIAD-EU laboratory of systemic multi-hazard risk assessment and management.
- We used the above outputs to develop the **Disaster Risk Gateway**, a Wiki-style online crowd-sourcing platform with a glossary of terms and definitions and examples of qualitative and quantitative approaches, including their application in practice (www.disasterriskgateway.net).

Recommendations

- **Terminology and definitions matter.** The MYRIAD-EU project comprises a multi-and interdisciplinary team, with different disciplinary backgrounds, experiences, and expertise. Establishing a common understanding is central to successful interdisciplinary research and practice.
- **When is it helpful to include the ‘multi-’ prefix?** We question whether part of the paradigm shift needed to successfully address complex challenges facing an interconnected world is through inherently seeing vulnerability, exposure and disaster risk through the lens of multiple, interrelated hazards.
- **Evolution of the terminology.** Within MYRIAD-EU, new definitions are likely to emerge or evolve as the research progresses. This dynamic is captured through the Disaster Risk Gateway which becomes a living resource with relevance within and beyond the project.
- **Indicator sets could be used to drive progress towards multi-hazard, multi-risk management.** Moreover, a systemic, integrated perspective of disaster risk management and adaptation could also support such future work. This requires indicators to be viewed through a multi-hazard, multi-risk lens as standard practice.

Context

The importance of a baseline and common understanding of definitions and concepts is essential to reporting progress on key international agreements including the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015-2030), the Paris Agreement on Climate Change and the Sustainable Development Goals of Agenda 2030. Disaster risk terminology has received a lot of attention over the last decades and there have been

several international endeavours to develop a common understanding of disaster risk related terminology led by intergovernmental bodies (e.g. UNDRR, ISC, IPCC, WHO, WMO). An essential first step of the MYRIAD-EU project was to build a common understanding of the current state of play of multi-hazard and multi-risk terminology, identify and recommend existing terminology to adopt, and identify gaps and opportunities for further terminology evolution. To this end, the 'Handbook of Multi-Hazard, Multi-Risk Definitions and Concepts' (referred to as 'Handbook') builds on existing work, using a multi-method approach to bring together data and insights from across and beyond the consortium (including literature reviews and curation of existing established glossaries). Where possible, we adopted language from established, intergovernmental glossaries to ensure our work and outputs align with national and international efforts to implement the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030. The Disaster Risk Gateway was developed to enable users to reflect on what additional benefits may arise from consulting existing tools, methods, or models; to increase understanding of what is currently possible, and how this knowledge can be applied in different sectors and/or for various multi-risk challenges; to introduce the hazards and risk practice community to existing research teams working on these issues as well as important past or present projects. The outputs of this work have key importance for both the MYRIAD-EU project process (interdisciplinary, knowledge co-development) and its impact.

The Disaster Risk Gateway Wiki-style platform logo

Want to know more?

- **Full reference:** Gill, J., Duncan, M., Ciurean, R., Smale, L., Stuparu, D., Schlumberger, J., de Ruiter, M., Tiggeloven, T., Torresan, S., Gottardo, S., Mysiak, J., Harris, R., Petrescu, E.-C., Girard, T., Khazai, B., Claassen, J., Dai, R., Champion, A., Daloz, A. S., ..., Ward, P. (2022). D1.2 Handbook of Multi-hazard, Multi-Risk Definitions and Concepts. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7870260>
- **Link to Disaster Risk Gateway:** www.disasterriskgateway.net
- **MYRIAD-EU website:** www.myriadproject.eu
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November 2023

Research brief: A review of current multi-risk governance practice in Europe

MYRIAD-EU project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003276

A review of current multi-risk governance practice in Europe

Highlights

- We developed a report on **policies, policy-making processes, and governance for multi-hazard, multi-risk management**, which investigates and reviews the current multi-risk governance practice in Europe.
- We identified a need in current governance practices to increase awareness of intersectoral interdependencies, i.e., how risks in one sector can propagate or amplify risks in another, especially under multi-hazard conditions.
- To address this knowledge gap, we systematically categorised **sectoral interdependencies** and provided a structure to navigate the intricate landscape of multi-sector risks, establishing a foundation for more effective Disaster Risk Management (DRM) planning.

Recommendations

- Science should make the step from conceptual frameworks to testing and operationalising approaches (Science).
- For new approaches, keep in mind the purpose and application context of these tools (Science & Practice).
- Integrate processes of multi-risk assessment and management (Science).
- Make use of existing knowledge and link to existing processes (Science & Practice).
- Engage in projects and initiatives that consider multi-risks (Science & Practice).
- Integrate considerations of (multi-)risk governance in strategies and long-term planning (Practice).
- It is recommended that sectors gauge a fuller understanding of their function failure points and integrate operational thresholds and uncertainties into decision making to reduce spillover effects.
- Risk assessment needs to be widened to not only consider 'domino effects' but also intersecting risks, which can combine to cause exacerbated risk in the long-term.
- DRM planning needs to think not only about immediate impacts and shorter-term solutions, but also impacts in the long-term.
- DRM strategies should also be adaptable and dynamic as the trajectory of spillover effects for example, are highly unpredictable.
- Further attention should be brought to the local societal context, and its adaptive capacity to shocks.

Context

Multi-risk assessment and governance are by their nature highly interdisciplinary pursuits, characterised by complex and interacting processes. This inherent complexity can pose difficulties for policy-makers and practitioners. Similarly, the field of multi-sector risk is highly complex and relatively understudied. Understanding the dynamic interaction of systems and inherent systemic risk is a considerable scientific challenge but is one that needs to be addressed to effectively identify and prepare for hazard events. This work

aimed at contributing towards a more holistic approach to risk management built on an overview of the current multi-risk policy and governance and an in-depth understanding of sectoral interdependencies. As the MYRIAD-EU project delves into multi-hazard and multi-risk realms, it is imperative to comprehend the variegated ways in which sectors influence one another. By elucidating the typologies of interdependencies, we not only address this knowledge deficit but also pave the way for designing robust policies and strategies that can manage these intricate interplays. This structure, therefore, builds the foundation upon which subsequent stakeholder discussions and Disaster Risk Management strategies can be anchored, ensuring that they are informed, comprehensive, and adaptive to the dynamic nature of multi-sector risks

An illustrative example of a multi-hazard scenario (2 consecutive cyclones), including multi-sector interdependency typologies

Want to know more?

- **Full reference:** Schlumberger, J., Stuparu, D., Ciurean, R. L., Duncan, M., Mysiak, J., Khazai, B., Rimmer, J., Dochiu, C., Claassen, J., & Warren, A. (2023). D1.3 Report on policies, policy-making processes, and governance for multi- hazard, multi-risk management (Version 2). Zenodo.
- **Link to paper:** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10001937>
- **MYRIAD-EU website:** www.myriadproject.eu
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- **Contact:** Julius Schlumberger (Julius.schlumberger@deltares.nl), Roxana Ciurean (roxan@bgs.ac.uk)

November 2023

Research brief: Development of a Systemic Multi-Hazard and Multi-risk Framework

MYRIAD-EU project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003276

MYRIAD-EU Framework: Development of a Systemic Multi-Hazard and Multi-risk Framework

Highlights

- We developed a six-steps framework for analysis and management of risk across a spectrum that ranges from single to multi- and systemic risk.
- We suggest two overarching dimensions, a specific system definition and the concept of dependencies, for a unifying multi-hazard and multi-risk framework.
 - The system definition enables a careful examination of the system boundaries which are crucial in determining how improvement will be measured for a given management option.
 - The dependencies concept, either hazard- or risk-related, enables an integration of single, multi- and systemic risks within the suggested system definition.
- Multi-hazards as well as multi-risks can be viewed as single risks in the case that there are no dependencies. Consequently, single and systemic risks can be viewed as two ends of a risk continuum where the increase in dependency is the overarching dimension for multi-risks.
- Guidance protocols were developed based on detailed stakeholder interactions to successfully navigate through the framework and each step.

Recommendations

Single-, multi- and systemic risks should not be seen in isolation but rather as a risk continuum that arises from different levels of dependency. A focus on dependencies, for the hazard, the dynamics of exposure and vulnerability, as well as possible impacts, should therefore be taken for the assessment of risk. Viewed from a systemic perspective, the so-called failures of elements in a system can be interpreted as events that cause consequences due to dependencies. The stronger the dependencies are, the more the system level will be affected. Dependencies therefore can also be used for risk management against individual failures as well as indirect consequences using bottom-up and top-down approaches.

Context

As recent hazard events have made apparent, natural hazards are often interconnected (e.g., compound or consecutive hazards) and their impacts can spread across geographical, administrative and sectoral boundaries in our increasingly interconnected world. These multi-hazard events lay bare the need for new ways of assessing and managing their associated risks and impacts. Most risk assessment and management approaches to date do not account for these types of hazards and the interrelationships between them. The MYRIAD-EU project sets out to fill the gaps within this field of risk research and bring about a paradigm shift in risk assessment and management which can be applied to multi-hazards and multi-risks.

Based on systemic risk ideas and the contribution of experts, a new framework for the assessment and management of systemic multi-hazard and multi-risks was developed (Hochrainer-Stigler et al. 2023). Rather than providing guidelines on how to apply pre-prescribed methods, tools, and approaches, the framework should be seen as guidance for the implementation of multi and systemic risk assessment and management. Depending on who applies the framework, different approaches and tools will prove more suitable than others, i.e., the solution to the issue at hand will be case-specific. A series of guiding questions, so-called guidance protocols, were drawn up to help in the implementation of the framework. The guidance protocols follow the structure of a stepwise analysis consisting of six steps: (1) finding a system definition, (2) characterization of direct risk, (3) characterization of indirect risk, (4) evaluation of direct and indirect risk, (5) defining risk management options, and (6) accounting for future system states (see Figure below). The framework is currently being tested in five MYRIAD-EU pilots, with feedback from stakeholders on the ground effectively shaping the iterative update of the framework.

Six-step framework for individual, multi-, and systemic risk analysis and management. Source: Hochrainer-Stigler et al. (2023).

Want to know more?

- **Full reference:** Hochrainer-Stigler, Stefan, Robert Šakić Trogrlić, Karina Reiter, Philip J. Ward, Marleen C. de Ruiter, Melanie J. Duncan, Silvia Torresan et al. "Toward a framework for systemic multi-hazard and multi-risk assessment and management." *Iscience* 26, no. 5 (2023).
- **Link to paper:** [https://www.cell.com/iscience/pdf/S2589-0042\(23\)00813-1.pdf](https://www.cell.com/iscience/pdf/S2589-0042(23)00813-1.pdf)
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November 2023

Research brief: Stakeholder perspective on disaster risk management challenges in five European Pilots

MYRIAD-EU project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003276

MYRIAD-EU Pilots: Stakeholder perspective on disaster risk management challenges in five European Pilots

Highlights

- **Pilot Leads have built solid relationships with their stakeholder networks.** This is an ongoing process, which required extensive efforts at the start of the project and evolved with a better understanding of the specific challenges and needs within each Pilot. For example, the lack of information and knowledge about the impacts of multi-hazards in their region, the difficulty of appropriately communicating complex science and its importance to non-scientific audiences, and the varied and competing stakeholder interests.
- **The first round of Pilot workshops was a success.** Consensus was reached on the importance of adopting a multi-risk approach in disaster risk management (DRM). Stakeholders helped prioritise the research questions to be addressed within their regions. Stakeholders confirmed their participation in the next engagement events (including focus groups and interviews).
- Stakeholder engagement in knowledge co-development lead to the identification of **five cross-Pilot DRM challenge themes:**
 - Inadequate governance of multi-hazards and multi-risks
 - Lack of knowledge of multi-hazards and multi-risks
 - Single-hazard and single-sector focus of the existing approach
 - Lack of data and information
 - The complexity of translating science into policy and practice
- **Specific methodological approaches are needed to address multi-faceted and interlinked DRM challenges in each Pilot.** These approaches are co-designed and tested in collaboration with stakeholders over the next project year. Results will be used to inform the multi-risk and multi-sector analysis and develop targeted disaster risk management pathways in each Pilot.

Recommendations

Based on the experience gained in MYRIAD-EU to date, especially through the involvement of stakeholders in research design and knowledge development in the five Pilots, the following recommendations are formulated:

- Engaging stakeholders in the multi-risk assessment and management process at the very onset is fundamental as it improves risk awareness and allows for priority setting
- A multi-hazard and multi-sector approach to DRM is necessary for taking interrelationships and interdependencies into account when developing effective risk reduction options; it also requires and promotes cooperation between institutions and can unlock development and economic potential for regions and communities
- Useful, usable, and used multi-risk assessment and management solutions should be co-designed considering their potential for down-, or up-scaling, where appropriate. This will ensure transferability to other sites and contexts.

Context

In MYRIAD-EU, various methodological approaches for multi-hazard risk assessment and management are co-developed and tested in practice in five European Pilots, i.e. Danube, Scandinavia, North Sea, Veneto, and Canary Islands (Figure 1). A continuous engagement with regional and local stakeholders is ensured for the duration of the entire project and reaches its high points at four events, an Initial and Final Pilot Workshop and two Focus Groups. The Pilots, with the support of the project coordinator team, scientific partners, and Sectoral Representatives, have dedicated the first two years of the project to: i) build the multi-risk profile and understand the governance/regulatory landscape of their region through a comprehensive stocktaking of existing data and information; ii) formulate the DRM challenges for their region after collecting stakeholders' perspectives, experiences, and needs via a series of workshops; and iii) select an appropriate combination of methods for multi-hazard risk assessment and management to (partially) respond to the identified challenges. In a recently submitted paper, we identify and analyse the DRM challenges resulting from the interaction with a vast array of stakeholders (and experts) in workshops organised across the Pilots.

• Figure 1. Overview of MYRIAD-EU Pilots

Want to know more?

- **Full reference:** Robert Šakić Trogrlić et al. Challenges in Assessing and Managing Multi-Hazard Risks: A European Stakeholders Perspective. Submitted to Environmental Sciences and Policy (September 2023)
- **MYRIAD-EU website:** www.myriadproject.eu
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November 2023

Research brief: The challenges of dynamic vulnerability and how to assess it

MYRIAD-EU project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003276

The challenges of dynamic vulnerability and how to assess it

Highlights

- We discuss the complex interactions between hazards and vulnerability and suggest methodological approaches to assess and include dynamics of vulnerability in our risk assessments, learning from the compound and multi-hazard, socio-hydrology, and socio-ecological research communities.
- To better understand the complexities of disasters, we need to change our perspective, starting from the circumstances that determine dynamic vulnerability.
- We identify three types of dynamics of vulnerability, namely:
 - the underlying dynamics of vulnerability,
 - changes in vulnerability during long-lasting disasters, and
 - changes in vulnerability during compounding disasters and societal shocks.
- We suggest that, while recognising the challenges of assessing dynamics of vulnerability, we can learn from the methods used in neighbouring fields.

Recommendations

- Growing attention to hazard dynamics in neighbouring research fields has led to the adoption of novel methods, including agent-based models, scenarios, and storylines, as well as qualitative approaches.
- We argue that many of these methods hold significant potential for capturing vulnerability dynamics.
- We categorise these methods into three groups based on their objectives:
 - Qualitative methods, such as narratives approach, which provide insights into underlying processes.
 - Agent-based models (ABMs) and System Dynamics, which can leverage insights from qualitative assessments.
 - Scenarios and storylines, which can build upon findings from ABMs and System Dynamic models to explore plausible future scenarios.

Context

Since the launch of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, there has been a notable effort to enhance our comprehension of risk dynamics. In recent times, this drive has spurred increased research within the compound and multi-hazard community, focusing on hazard dynamics. However, a comparatively less explored aspect of risk is that of the dynamics of vulnerability. Around the turn of the century, researchers recognised the intricacies of vulnerability, particularly when transitioning from physical to social perspectives. Subsequent years saw notable developments in vulnerability research, including shifts in indicators, expanding the scope from physical to social vulnerability, and a recent emphasis on dynamic vulnerability. Moreover, distinguishing between social processes as hazards and sources of vulnerability has become increasingly blurred.

We pinpoint three often-overlooked aspects of vulnerability dynamics in risk assessments. These dynamics can extend across vast spatial and temporal scales, posing challenges for both the general public and policymakers in comprehending their intricacies. Integrating these aspects into dynamic risk assessments presents a challenge for researchers. Hence, we explore potential methods drawn from neighbouring fields.

Illustration/Graph/Picture

Fig. 1. Three key types of dynamics of vulnerability

The panels show from left to right: underlying dynamics of vulnerability, such as (internal) migration, conflicts, or economic recession (A); dynamics during long-lasting vulnerability, such as effects of (mal)adaptation, eroding financial resources, or mental well-being (B); and dynamics of vulnerability owing to consecutive or compound disasters, such as the effects of an earlier hazard on the vulnerability at the time of a second hazard (C).

Want to know more?

- **Full reference:** de Ruiter, M. C., & Van Loon, A. F. (2022). The challenges of dynamic vulnerability and how to assess it. *IScience*, 25(8).
- **Link to paper:** [https://www.cell.com/iscience/pdf/S2589-0042\(22\)00992-0.pdf](https://www.cell.com/iscience/pdf/S2589-0042(22)00992-0.pdf)
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November 2023

Research brief: Revolutionising Multi-Hazard Risk Assessment: Innovative Methods for a Safer Tomorrow

MYRIAD-EU project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003276

Revolutionising Multi-Hazard Risk Assessment: Innovative Methods for a Safer Tomorrow

Highlights

- **Comprehensive Vulnerability Database:** A database for six urban hazards reveals insights into commonalities and differences in vulnerability drivers, informing targeted risk reduction strategies.
- **Data Innovation for Impact Analysis:** Novel data sources like Google Trends offer real-time understanding of public response during extreme events, aiding timely interventions.
- **Advanced Techniques for Risk Assessment:** Machine Learning, analysis of Nighttime Lights (NTL) data, and disaster forensic approaches provide evidence-based insights, improving multi-hazard risk management and resilience planning.

Recommendations

1. **Strengthen Data Infrastructure:**
 - Invest in improving data quality and availability, particularly for hazard, exposure, vulnerability, and impact data.
 - Collaborate internationally to create comprehensive, standardised global datasets and reporting frameworks.
2. **Utilise Emerging Data Sources:**
 - Leverage novel data sources such as NTL data and Google Trends to enhance risk assessment and public awareness during extreme events.
 - Invest in tools and resources for higher-resolution data analysis.
3. **Enhance Risk Understanding:**
 - Support comprehensive disaster forensic analysis to identify root causes and vulnerabilities, enabling informed policy decisions and risk reduction strategies.
 - Develop high-quality, high-resolution multi-risk event datasets to advance Machine Learning applications for more accurate multi-hazard risk assessments.
4. **Promote Multi-Hazard Awareness:**
 - Educate the general public, businesses, and stakeholders about multi-hazard events to foster a broader understanding of interconnected risks and encourage preparedness efforts.

Context

Natural hazards pose significant threats to communities worldwide, and addressing these challenges has never been more crucial. Traditional approaches to risk assessment, which often focus on individual hazards in isolation, are inadequate in today's inter connected world. The MYRIAD-EU project recognises the pressing need to shift our approach from single-hazard assessments to a comprehensive understanding of multi-hazard dynamics.

Therefore, we explore innovative methods and data sources employed by MYRIAD -EU to assess risk dynamics and feedbacks between risk components in a multi-hazard context. We address the need for a holistic risk framework, encompassing hazard analysis, exposure, vulnerability, and response, to enhance decision-making across diverse sectors. By considering interactions between multiple hazards and the implementation of disaster risk reduction (DRR) measures, this research aids risk managers and decision-makers in preparing for and recovering from multi-hazard risk events.

Illustration/Graph/Picture

Dynamics of (urban) vulnerability. Each graph shows the relationship between a vulnerability driver and the impact of a hazard.

Want to know more?

- **Full reference:** de Ruyter, M., Jäger, W., Buijs, S., Tiggeloven, T., Stolte, T., De Polt, K., Critto, A., Torresan, S., Maraschini, M., Sano, M., Ferrario, D. M., Daniel, J., Khazai, B., & Sakic Troglic, R. (2023). Report on Novel Methods for Detecting Empirical Evidence of Dynamics & Feedbacks of Risk Drivers. Deliverable 4.3, report, MYRIAD-EU project.
- **Link to paper:** <https://zenodo.org/records/8329001>
- **MYRIAD-EU website:** www.myriadproject.eu
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November 2023

Research brief: Impact-relevant climate hazard durations

MYRIAD-EU project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003276

MYRIAD-EU Pilots: Impact-relevant climate hazard durations

Highlights

- We have developed a methodology to determine impact-relevant durations for the analysis of climate extremes based upon local context of impacts.
- Duration was determined to be an important factor to consider, alongside temperature, when investigating impacts from extreme heat events.
- A successful case study was carried out where we determined heatwave durations of 2 weeks to 2 months as the time periods in which the greatest societal impacts occur in Germany.

Recommendations

The results of this analysis support the recommendation that those planning hazard and impact analyses should be informed about the time period over which the metrics should be averaged. Averaging metrics over the most impact-relevant durations will lead to a more informed understanding of hazard and impact relationships. The methods developed in this study can be extended to other impact metrics, regions and hazard types to provide more meaningful definitions of climate extremes, guiding future research and a more localised understanding of these events.

Context

In impact analyses, it is common to see differences in how hazards are defined or quantified. This issue is particularly pronounced in the study of heat waves due to unclear and varying definitions, which hinders the comparability of studies. These differences mainly relate to the time scale used to measure the metrics. Heat waves are typically described as periods of consecutive days with above-normal air temperatures.

In our study, we developed and applied a method to create a more relevant, localised means of quantifying heatwaves through impact-relevant durations. As a case study, we focused on Germany and examined the impact of extreme heat on two key sectors: public health and societal attention. We used modelled meteorological data and observed impact datasets, and applied statistical analysis to derive our findings.

Figure: Schematic overview of the approach used to identify impact-relevant heatwave durations

Want to know more?

- **Full reference:** De Polt, Ward, de Ruiter, Bogdanovich, Reichstein, Frank, and Orth (2023) *Quantifying impact-relevant heat wave durations*. *Environ. Res. Lett.*
- **Link to paper:** <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/acf05e>
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November 2023

Research brief: Collaborative systems approaches: Guidance for Pilots on collaborative systems analysis tools and approaches for complex, multi-hazard, multi-sector systems

MYRIAD-EU project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003276

Collaborative systems approaches: Guidance for Pilots on collaborative systems analysis tools and approaches for complex, multi-hazard, multi-sector systems

Highlights

- We highlight findings from a review of promising tools and approaches for collaborative systems analysis.
- We propose a flexible, generic collaborative multi-sector, multi-risk system analysis approach for complex, multi-hazard, multi-sector systems consisting of three principal iterative steps in which the complexity of the system is gradually built up. Suggestions on appropriate methods and tools are provided for each step.
- We highlight how the various activities of the approach relate to the steps of the MYRIAD-EU framework for systemic multi-hazard and multi-risk assessment and management.
- We summarise reflections from the initial deployment of collaborative systems analysis tools and approaches during the first round of pilot workshops in the five MYRIAD-EU pilots.

Recommendations

- **Fit-for-purpose approach:** Based on initial feedback from the pilots, the proposed approach appears fit-for-purpose, but we recognise the complete approach could not yet be implemented in the pilots at this early stage. We look forward to receiving further feedback on the proposed approach, methods and tools as the pilots elaborate these analyses together with their stakeholders during subsequent meetings in MYRIAD-EU.
- **Effective facilitation:** The proposed approach demands strong and effective facilitation to lead discussions and help to synthesise system complexities for stakeholders.
- **Time allocated to systems analysis:** Sufficient time must be allocated to systems analysis activities in order to explore the full complexity of systems and to generate the necessary stakeholder consensus on system functions, objectives, and characteristics.

Context

Collaborative systems analysis approaches are needed for forward-looking adaptive multi-risk decision making for a variety of reasons, including (i) to avoid negative consequences when approaching problems through a sector-specific lens, (ii) to aid in the formulation of system-wide objectives that both recognise and balance the inherent trade-offs within our systems, (iii) to ensure a more equitable distribution of system-wide resources, costs and benefits, and (iv) to help reduce the potential for stakeholder conflict.

In this light, the principal purpose of collaborative systems analysis approaches is to help describe decision-making contexts in all their complexity.

Based on the findings of our review, we conclude that systems analysis tools and approaches that permit complete systems analyses offer the most promising avenues for complex, multi-hazard, multi-sector systems. Accordingly, our proposed collaborative systems analysis approach aims to capture full system complexity by gradually building this up across three, iterative steps:

1. Defining system boundaries and constraints
2. Undertaking sector-based analyses
3. Synthesising sector-based analyses into a whole-of-system analysis

Within the approach, particular emphasis is placed upon establishing an agreed set of (measurable) sector and system objectives (i.e., definitions of success), as these are critical ingredients to both assess and evaluate risks via the MYRIAD-EU framework and for the systematic development of multi-risk pathways via the DAPP-MR methodology.

Caption: Proposed collaborative systems analysis approach to be applied in MYRIAD -EU

Want to know more?

- **Full references:** Warren, A., Stuparu, D., Schlumberger, J., Tijssen, A., Dochiu, C., Rimmer, J., 2022. Guidance document for Pilots on collaborative systems analysis approaches. [MYRIAD-EU Deliverable 6.2](#).

- Warren, A., Schlumberger, J., 2023. D6.3. Interim report on collaborative systems and DAPP approaches to develop forward looking DRM pathways. [MYRIAD-EU Deliverable 6.3](#).
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November 2023

Research brief: Proposing DAPP-MR as a disaster risk management pathways framework for complex, dynamic multi-risk

MYRIAD-EU project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003276

Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways for Multi-Risk (DAPP-MR): Proposing DAPP-MR as a disaster risk management pathways framework for complex, dynamic multi-risk

Highlights

- We emphasise the growing complexity of natural hazards due to overlapping risks across different sectors, highlighting a gap in Disaster Risk Management (DRM) strategies to address these interconnected, uncertain risk drivers for strategic planning.
- We propose a novel approach, Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways for Multi-Risk (DAPP-MR), tailored and proposed to design DRM pathways catering to dynamic multi-risk, handling multi-hazard and multi-sector challenges.
- Using a stylised case, DAPP-MR is shown to guide analysis processes in a stepwise manner towards integrating knowledge essential for multi-risk DRM.

Recommendations

- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Successful multi-risk DRM requires an inter- and transdisciplinary approach, integrating insights from natural, technical, social, and political sciences alongside local knowledge and practices. This collaboration can foster better understanding and management of complex multi-risk systems, and promote the co-production of knowledge and new risk governance practices.
- **Practical Implementation and Testing:** Real-world testing of DAPP-MR, involving stakeholders, is necessary to validate the framework. This includes investigating how to deal with contested objectives, complex dependencies, and accounting for institutional characteristics to ensure fairness, practicality and effectiveness of the proposed framework. The DAPP-MR approach is now being tested within the MYRIAD-EU project in several Pilot regions, namely: North Sea, Canary Islands, and Scandinavia.
- **Engagement and Representation:** The operationalisation of DAPP-MR demands further research, especially in identifying the limits of complexity and managing uncertainties inherent in multi-risk systems. Research should also explore how to embed DAPP-MR in practical decision-making processes, aiming for an effective operational decision support tool for complex multi-risk DRM.

Context

Pathways thinking can help design robust and flexible long-term DRM strategies, broken down into manageable steps, to navigate the complexity of unknown future states of the world and interaction of multiple hazards, various sectors, and measures. It embraces the dynamism between hazards and sector responses, tackling uncertainties head-on. The intertwining of hazards and sectors could result in cascading impacts, magnifying the challenges and requiring a broader, more integrated approach to DRM. This cooperative

approach could both help to unravel these intricacies and also better equip stakeholders in planning and responding to risks in a collective, more informed manner. The DAPP-MR approach was developed as a tool to assist in this process.

Caption: The proposed DAPP-MR framework for the analysis of DRM pathways in a multi-risk setting

Caption: Exemplary pathways and their changes depending on whether they are developed for single-hazard risks or multi-risk (bottom).

Want to know more?

- **Full reference:** Schlumberger, J., Haasnoot, M., Aerts, J., & De Ruiter, M. (2022). Proposing DAPP-MR as a disaster risk management pathways framework for complex, dynamic multi-risk. *Iscience*, 25(10), 105219.
- **Link to paper:** <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.105219>
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3 Communication highlights

3.1 Project website

One of the main communication-dissemination channels for MYRIAD-EU is the project website: <https://www.myriadproject.eu/>. The website was set up at the beginning of the project and went online in August 2018. The website was created in line with the visual identity and receives contributions from members of the consortium. The website contains sections on 'News' and 'Events', where the most relevant news about the project and upcoming events are published. Since November 2021, 38 articles have been published on the website.

3.2 X (formally Twitter) account

The account was created in September 2021 and currently has 1,475 followers. In March 2023, the account posted its best performing tweet which received 11,000 impressions. The tweet featured a short clip highlighting MYRIAD-EU involvement at EGU 2023 in Vienna.

3.3 LinkedIn account

In early October 2023, The MYRIAD-EU LinkedIn account was created, the page officially went live on 10th October. The account currently has 88 followers. Since the page has been created, three posts have been published, these posts have received over 2,400 impressions. The post that received the most attention was related to an article co-written by members of MYRIAD-EU from CICERO and Wetlands International, which received 47 reactions and 4 retweets.

3.4 Newsletter

The first MYRIAD-EU newsletter was sent out on the 28th September 2023. The newsletter will be sent out every 3 months and will provide a means of informing the wider MYRIAD-EU community of project developments and research publications. The first newsletter featured an editorial by the Project Coordinator, two articles by members of the Consortium as well as upcoming conferences and events. The newsletter was sent to 168 people and received very positive feedback.

3.5 Events

The large consortium is active in taking part in numerous scientific, policy, and practice events, to disseminate and to raise awareness of MYRIAD-EU in various capacities. They include: several major scientific conferences (e.g. EGU General Assembly 2021, 2022, 2023 in Vienna, ECCA 2023 in Dublin, Adaptation Futures 2023 in Montreal); high-level policy-events (e.g. UNDRR European Forum for Disaster Risk Reduction, 7th DRMKC Annual Seminar in Brussels); and several practice-oriented events (e.g., FEHRL Members Workshop, and HOTREC annual assembly).

Currently, MYRIAD-EU in collaboration with RiskKAN and NatRiskChange is working on organisation of the 3rd International Conference on Natural Hazards and Risks in a Changing World: Addressing Compound and Multi-Hazard Risk, which will take place on 12-14 June 2024 in Amsterdam. The conference website was published in late October 2023; www.ChangingWorldRisks2024.eu.

Selected list of scientific papers to date

- Claassen, J.N., Ward, P.J., Daniell, J., Koks, E.E., Tiggeloven, T., De Ruiter, M.C., 2023. A new method to compile global multi-hazard event sets. *Scientific Reports*, 13, 13808, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-40400-5>
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- De Ruiter, M.C, van Loon, A.F., 2022. The challenges of dynamic vulnerability and how to assess it. *iScience*, 25, 104720, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.104720>,
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- De Ruiter, M.C., Couasnon, A., Ward, P. J.: *Breaking the Silos: an online serious game for multi-risk disaster risk reduction (DRR) management*. *Geoscience Communication*. 4, 383-397, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gc-4-383-2021>Li, H., Haer, T., Couasnon, A., Enríquez, A.R., Muis, S., Ward, P.J., 2023. A spatially-dependent synthetic global dataset of extreme sea level events. *Weather and Climate Extremes*, 41, 100596, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wace.2023.100596>
- Kreibich, H., Van Loon, A.F., Schröter, K., Ward, P.J., Mazzoleni, M., Sairam, N., Abeshu, G.W., Agafonova, S., AghaKouchak, A., Aksoy, H., Alvarez-Garretón, C., Aznar, B., Balkhi, L., Barendrecht, M.H., Biancamaria, S., Bos-Burgering, L., Bradley, C., Budiyo, Y., Buytaert, W., Capewell, L., Carlson, H., Cavus, Y., Couasnon, A., Coxon, G., Daliakopoulos, I., de Ruiter, M.C., Delus, C., Erfurt, M., Esposito, G., François, D., Frappart, F., Freer, J., Frolova, N., Gain, A.K., Grillakis, M., Grima, J.O., Guzmán, D.A., Huning, L.S., Ionita, M., Kharlamov, M., Khoi, D.N., Kieboom, N., Kireeva, M., Koutroulis, A., Lavado-Casimiro, W., Li, H.-Y., Carmen Llasat, M., Macdonald, D., Mård, J., Mathew-Richards, H., McKenzie, A., Mejia, A., Mendiondo, E.M., Mens, M., Mobini, S., Mohor, G.S., Nagavciuc, V., Ngo-Duc, T., Huynh, T.T.N., Nhi., P.T.T., Petrucci, O., Nguyen, H.Q., Quintana-Seguí, P., Razavi, S., Ridolfi, E., Riegel, J., Sadik, M.S., Savelli, E., Sazonov, A., Sharma, S., Sørensen, J., Arguello Souza, F.A., Stahl, K., Steinhausen, M., Stoelzle, M., Szalińska, W., Tang, Q., Tian, F., Tokarczyk, T., Tovar, C., Tran, T.V.T., Van Huijgevoort, M.H.J., van Vliet, M.T.H., Vorogushyn, S., Wagener, T., Wang, Y., Wendt, D.E., Wickham, E., Yang, L., Zambrano-Bigiarini, M., Blöschl, G., Di Baldassarre, G., 2022. *Nature*, 608, 80-86, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04917-5>
- Matanó, A., de Ruiter, M.C., Koehler, J., Ward, P.J., Van Loon, A.F., 2022. Caught between extremes: Understanding human-water interactions during drought-to-flood events in the Horn of Africa. *Earth's Future*, 10, e2022EF002747, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022EF002747>

3.6 List of public deliverables

- Ciurean, R. et al., 2022. Disaster Risk Gateway, MYRIAD-EU project [Deliverable 1.1](#)
- Gill, J.C. et al. 2022. Handbook of Multi-Hazard, Multi-Risk Definitions and Concepts. MYRIAD-EU project [Deliverable 1.2](#)
- Schlumberger, J. et al., 2022. Report on policies, policy-making processes, and governance for multi-hazard, multi-risk management. MYRIAD-EU project [Deliverable 1.3](#)
- Hochrainer-Stigler, S. et al., 2022. Initial Framework and Guidance Protocol Document. MYRIAD-EU project [Deliverable 2.1](#)
- De Ruiter, M.C. et al., 2023. Report on Novel Methods for Detecting Empirical Evidence of Dynamics & Feedbacks of Risk Drivers. MYRIAD-EU [Deliverable 4.3](#)
- Warren, A., Schlumberger, J., 2023. Interim report on collaborative systems and DAPP approaches to develop forward looking DRM pathways. MYRIAD-EU [Deliverable D6.3](#)
 - Ward, P.J. et al., 2023. [MYRIAD-EU Periodic Technical Report M1-18](#)

4 Outlook

The workflow in MYRIAD-EU is divided into five major steps: (1) common baseline; (2) initial design and development; (3) iterative testing and refinement; (4) finalisation; and (5) legacy (Figure 3). During the second half of the project, MYRIAD-EU will enter the final three stages: iterative testing and refinement, finalisation, and legacy.

In Month 25, the initial versions of the methods and tools developed in the WPs of the Thematic Track were successfully presented to the Pilots by means of a webinar with the Helpdesks of WP4-6. In the coming period, these methods and tools will be tested in the Pilots, together with the Pilot core user group, and feedback will be provided iteratively to the WPs of the Thematic Track so that the methods and tools can be refined. Each Pilot will hold two focus groups (around Months 27 and 36) to discuss the interim research products and Pilot results and to obtain suggestions on how these could be improved in the finalisation phase. Based on these focus groups, suggestions for improving the overall framework will be fed back to WP2, which will update the guidance protocols accordingly. Iterative feedback between the Pilot Track and Thematic Track is provided by the Helpdesks.

On 12-14 June 2024, MYRIAD-EU will co-host the conference *Natural Hazards and Risks in a Changing World: Addressing Compound and Multi-Hazard Risk*, together with RiskKAN and NatRiskChange (<http://www.changingworldrisks2024.eu>). The conference will take place in Amsterdam, the Netherlands. The main conference will take place on 12-13 June 2024 at the 'Rode Hoed' venue, and will consist of plenary and parallel sessions. It is aimed at researchers, scientists, risk practitioners in the field of disaster risk management and climate change adaptation. The purpose of this conference is to address the challenges posed by compound climate events and multi-hazard risk in a changing world and discuss methods for designing effective solutions to these challenges. On 14 June 2024 we plan to hold a dedicated ECR networking day, which will take place at Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (the coordinator of MYRIAD-EU). It will be aimed at, and organised by, a team of ECRs.

In the fifth and final step, we will focus predominantly on legacy activities that are designed to maximise impact beyond the end of the project. Work on MYRIAD-EU's legacy commenced during the first half of the project but will continue more strongly during the second half. First, a collaboration between different EU-funded multi-(hazard)-risk projects (namely, PARATUS, MIRACA, The HuT, MEDiate, C2IMPRESS, CLIMAXX, KNOWING, ICARIA, CORE) was initiated by MYRIAD-EU. During the EGU23 conference, a first meeting took place between all project leads and/or relevant WP leads from relevant projects to identify avenues for collaboration. Second, the former ECRB chairs (Judith Claassen and Kelley De Polt) established a group of ECR representatives from these different projects who will organise meetings and workshops during the project. This collaboration will likely create long lasting collaborations beyond the duration of the individual projects.

During the legacy phase, several other activities will be carried out, including: a synthesis paper, a policy workshop, policy briefs targeted at the different sectors involved in MYRIAD-EU, and a summer school.